

Critical Infrastructure Protection in the Water Sector

A 2030 Outlook

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1. Drivers of Critical Infrastructure Protection in the Water Sector

The access to clean and safe drinking water is a fundamental right in EU. Contaminated drinking water can lead to outbreaks of waterborne diseases^{1,2}, such as cholera, typhoid fever, and salmonella, bacteria, such as E. coli, and other pathogens that threaten human health. Protecting against chemical, biological, and radiological contaminants is also an important part of protecting public health. Water utilities must have emergency response plans if the water supply is interrupted as a result of natural disasters, terrorism, or system failures to facilitate the continuous service of drinking water supplies or the rapid restoration of water supplies, so it is safe to drink. Hence, the infrastructure of drinking water systems also comes under the European Critical Infrastructure Directive (2008/114/EC) and the EU Civil Protection Mechanism.

The drivers of **critical infrastructure protection (CIP)** in the **drinking water sector** are essential factors that ensure the safety, security, and resilience of water systems. These drivers focus on safeguarding water infrastructure from threats, both natural and man-made, to ensure reliable access to clean drinking water. The key drivers include:

Complex Regulatory and Policy Frameworks: EU has built a regulatory framework that consists of EU-wide directives and national-level implementations. The Drinking Water Directive (DWD) 2020/2184 ensures the quality of water intended for human consumption across the EU, setting maximum limits for contaminants, and introducing a holistic risk assessment covering the entire water supply chain. The directive is complemented by the partly overlapping:

- Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (91/271/EEC) regulating wastewater treatment
- Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) regulating inland and coastal waters
- Bathing Water Directive (2006/7/EC) regulating water quality in recreational waters
- Groundwater Directive (2006/118/EC) regulating groundwater, a key source of drinking water

Other supporting regulations and initiatives include the Regulation on Food Safety and Drinking Water (Regulation (EC) No 178/2002), EU Drinking Water Guidance on Water Reuse (2020), and the European Green Deal. Finally, national legislation on water management ensures coverage of country-specific needs, water resources, and environmental conditions.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Devon_cryptosporidiosis_outbreak

² <https://www.ekathimerini.com/news/1240477/water-network-to-blame-for-gastroenteritis-cases-in-central-greece-eody-finds/>

Sustainability Goals: A new European directive proposal for urban wastewater treatment³ plants will require them to produce the energy they consume, setting a precedent that could eventually extend to drinking water treatment plants. In this case, additional complexity will be added to water treatment facilities, necessitating large-scale energy regeneration systems. Such an event will necessitate infrastructures to extend their resilience plans to protect the additional facilities from both physical and cyber threats which could disrupt operations and compromise water quality.

Evolving Threat Landscape: Critical infrastructure related to drinking water is subject to several threats that are constantly increasing in terms of frequency, complexity and severity. The threats may have man-made or natural causes. Man-made disasters can be physical, cyber, or even hybrid. The potential for physical attacks, such as tampering or sabotage, drives the need for secure water facilities, chemical storage protection, and monitoring systems. On the other hand, as water systems are becoming more digitized and interconnected, they are deemed vulnerable to cyberattacks, including ransomware, data breaches, and disruption of automated systems. Telluric and climate related events also pose a threat for drinking water facilities. Hurricanes, earthquakes, floods, and other extreme weather events can disrupt water supplies and contaminate sources. Protecting infrastructure from these risks is essential to maintaining public health and safety. Changing weather patterns, droughts, and rising sea levels may also affect water availability and quality, necessitating robust water resource management and adaptation strategies.

Rapid Digitization and Automation: Drinking water infrastructure is rapidly digitized employing advanced sensors, remote monitoring technologies, and IoT devices to detect leaks, contamination, or system failures in real-time, transforming them into smart infrastructure. Many drinking water utilities rely on Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems to manage water treatment and distribution. Ensuring the cybersecurity of these systems is a growing concern as new vulnerabilities arise. Further, the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning for predictive maintenance and anomaly detection in water systems drives the need for resilient technological infrastructures. The trustworthiness and reliability of these models are essential requirements for critical infrastructures.

Interdependency with Other Sectors: Water utilities are heavily dependent on the energy grid for pumping, treating, and distributing water. Thus, power outages can disrupt water services, making the interdependency with the energy sector a key driver for protection. Further, water treatment chemicals and repair supplies rely on transportation and logistics systems that can face anomalies. On the other hand, disruptions in the water supply can have major economic impacts, especially for industries reliant on water, such as agriculture, food processing, and manufacturing. Critical domains such as hospitals, fire departments, and emergency services could paralyze without access to water.

Funding and Resources Scarcity: Aging water infrastructure is a major concern in many regions. Investment in modernizing water systems, including upgrading pipes, treatment plants, and digital systems, is a driver of critical infrastructure protection. Due to the limited public funding, especially in areas with lower income population, water management organizations (usually public entities) have a lack of human resources, especially highly skilled and technology proficient ones.

Economic Considerations: Protecting infrastructure from damage is more cost-effective than responding to disasters or attacks. Hence, the economic incentive drives continuous investment in infrastructure protection.

³ <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-7108-2024-INIT/en/pdf>

Public Awareness and Community Resilience: Public awareness about water security and conservation can help communities be more resilient in the face of threats. It is widely accepted that cooperation between local governments, water utilities, and communities can foster the development of resilience strategies and disaster preparedness.

These drivers form the foundation for effective protection strategies in the drinking water sector, focusing on safety, resilience, and the capacity to respond to emerging risks. This whitepaper discusses the challenges and provides recommendations for water management infrastructures.

2. Challenges and Limitations

Some of the main challenges and limitation faced by drinking water management organizations in the scope of their cyber-security and critical infrastructure protection efforts include:

Challenge 1: Aging and Dispersed Infrastructure: Many drinking water systems rely on infrastructure, including old pipelines and treatment plants, that is decades or even centuries old. In some cases, leakage can account for more than 25% of water loss, putting in danger the quality and availability of drinking water, while having financial implications. New technologies must integrate with legacy infrastructure, which can be challenging when dealing with outdated systems that may not be compatible. Further, modern water management requires handling large volumes of data from sensors, treatment facilities, and distribution networks, but many utilities struggle with proper data collection, storage, and analysis. Moreover, the wide geographical dispersion of the infrastructure, often in remote or hard to reach locations, can make it challenging to effectively monitor and protect it from physical threats and ensure robust communication capabilities. Reliance on telephone calls to communicate, especially with aging personnel, can hinder rapid emergency response. Introducing new, cyber-secure communication technologies and providing training in these tools is essential to ensure effective communication between all parties during emergencies.

Challenge 2: Extreme Climate Events: Extreme weather events like floods or hurricanes that can overwhelm water systems, leading to contamination, disruption of service, and damage to infrastructure, are becoming more frequent and bigger in scale. On the other hand, long droughts combined with the increased demand from agriculture, industry, and growing populations results in reduced water availability and strain on existing water resources. Over- and under-utilization of the water management infrastructure can lead to the deterioration of the quality of drinking water.

Challenge 3: Contamination and Emerging Pollutants: Groundwater, a critical source of drinking water in many regions, is vulnerable to contamination from industrial chemicals, pesticides, and other pollutants. Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) is a significant emerging concern as they are connected to negative effects on human health. Open water reservoirs such as lakes and rivers, which are also critical for drinking water supply for big cities, are susceptible too. Runoff from agriculture and urban areas contributes to nutrient pollution, leading to harmful algal blooms that can release toxins into drinking water sources. New contaminants such as pharmaceuticals, microplastics, and endocrine disruptors are not always covered by existing water quality regulations, making detection and treatment almost impossible.

Challenge 4: Evolving Cybersecurity Threats: As drinking water management organizations adopt digital technologies and smart water meters, they become more vulnerable to cyberattacks that could disrupt service, manipulate data, or contaminate water supplies. Many water utilities lack the resources or expertise to properly secure their digital infrastructure, leaving them exposed to ransomware and other threats.

Challenge 5: Cross-Sector Interdependency: Drinking water infrastructures have a high energy demand for water distribution and treatment, which adds operational vulnerabilities. Water often travels long distances, and although gravity is sometimes used to assist distribution, large pumping stations are essential for reaching remote or elevated areas. These stations and water gates, needed to manage flow according to demands, increase the energy requirements and operational costs. High energy demands expose infrastructure to risks from energy supply disruptions. Water companies could consider integrating energy regeneration methods, such as hydroelectric plants, to reduce reliance on external power sources and enhance resilience against energy disruptions. The extra facilities would compose new risks to the water treatment and supply.

Challenge 6: Public Health and Safety Risks: Outbreaks of waterborne diseases, such as cholera or legionella, pose significant public health risks if contamination occurs due to inadequate treatment or system failures. Managing rapid response to emergencies, such as contamination, natural disasters, or infrastructure failures, requires robust plans, trained personnel, and resources that are often lacking in smaller or underfunded utilities. Therefore, ensuring equitable access to clean drinking water, particularly for low-income and rural communities, remains a persistent challenge.

Challenge 7: Aging Workforce, Shortages and Skills Gaps: Integrating modern technologies, such as advanced water treatment, smart sensors, and AI-driven predictive maintenance, can be costly and require specialized expertise that smaller utilities may lack. Many water management organizations face a workforce nearing retirement, with a shortage of skilled professionals available to fill critical roles in engineering, maintenance, and cybersecurity. The complexity of modern water systems requires a highly skilled workforce and efficient communication, but training programs may be insufficient, particularly in smaller utilities or developing regions.

Challenge 8: Funding and Economic Constraints: Many water utilities, especially in low-income or rural areas, operate with limited financial resources, making it difficult to maintain infrastructure, invest in new technologies, or ensure compliance with regulations. Water is often heavily subsidized, which can limit the funds available for maintenance, upgrades, or expansion of water services. The reluctance to increase water tariffs, due to its essential value, can exacerbate these issues. Tensions between privatization and public control of water utilities can complicate funding strategies, service quality, and long-term sustainability.

Challenge 9: Regulatory Compliance and Governance: Water management organizations must comply with numerous local, national, and international regulations, which can be complex and sometimes conflicting, requiring significant resources for monitoring and reporting. In some regions, regulations may exist, but enforcement is weak, leading to non-compliance and continued risks to water safety. In addition, slow decision-making processes within regulatory bodies can hinder the implementation of necessary upgrades or responses to emerging threats.

Challenge 10: Political and Institutional Challenges: Water management organizations often operate in a political environment where priorities may shift, impacting funding, regulatory support, or long-term planning efforts. Moreover, in some regions, water management responsibilities are divided among multiple agencies, creating coordination issues and inefficiencies.

Addressing these (not exhaustive) challenges requires a multifaceted approach involving increased investment, and innovative technological and policy solutions.

3. Solution Guidelines: Towards new CIP Capabilities and Resilience

To improve drinking water infrastructure protection and resilience, organizations must adopt a comprehensive approach that integrates physical, cyber, operational, and environmental considerations. Below are key **guidelines** to contribute towards better protection and resilience of drinking water infrastructure:

3.1. Technical and Technological Guidelines

Guideline 1: Conduct Comprehensive Risk Assessments: Evaluate the full spectrum of risks, including natural disasters (e.g., floods, earthquakes), cybersecurity threats, terrorism, infrastructure failures, and climate change impacts. Including both physical and digital infrastructure in the risk analysis and assessing vulnerabilities across the entire water supply chain from source to consumer is obligatory. Forward-looking risk scenarios and assessment of their potential impact on the infrastructure, including the likelihood of multiple crises and cascade events, must be developed.

Guideline 2: Develop Robust Emergency Preparedness and Response Plans: The creation of emergency response plans that cover a wide range of threats, including natural disasters, chemical spills, and contamination incidents is required. Further, clear communication and coordination channels with local and national emergency services for faster response during crises must be established. Finally, the identification and securing of alternative water sources (e.g., groundwater, desalination plants) is required to establish emergency distribution networks in case of service disruption.

Guideline 3: Implement a Risk-Based Approach to Water Quality: A source-to-tap approach, assessing risks across the entire water supply system, from catchment areas to consumer taps is recommended. This involves protecting source water, monitoring treatment processes, and safeguarding distribution systems from human threats (e.g., terrorism). Regular monitoring for contaminants, including emerging pollutants (e.g., microplastics, pharmaceuticals) and biological threats (e.g., algal blooms, bacteria) needs to be established. Water treatment facilities must have multiple layers of protection (e.g., UV, filtration, chlorination) to address different types of contamination and redundant facilities should be deployed. Moreover, real-time monitoring tools to detect anomalies are essential in this effort.

Guideline 4: Enhanced Cybersecurity Measures: While norm DIN EN 17075 specifies laboratory methods for water quality tests, norms should be enhanced to include cybersecurity guidelines for the operation of online measurement methods and equipment, offering better protection of the system's digital aspects. IT and IoT networks that manage water distribution, treatment, and monitoring must be protected by firewalls, encryption, and smart intrusion detection systems. Regular cybersecurity audits, including penetration testing, to identify vulnerabilities and ensure compliance with the latest cybersecurity standards (e.g., the EU NIS2 Directive) are required. Moreover, water management authorities should develop and regularly update cybersecurity response protocols to handle potential breaches or attacks without disrupting water service.

Guideline 5: Maintain, Upgrade and Modernize Infrastructure: Regular, timely maintenance is key to prevent water leaks and contamination. Water management authorities should prioritize the replacement or repair of old, failing pipelines, treatment plants, and storage facilities to reduce the risk of contamination, water loss, and system breakdowns. In parallel, the use of sensors,

smart meters, and AI-powered monitoring tools to detect leaks, optimize water distribution, and predict equipment failure is essential. The upgrades should also include redundant power and backup systems to ensure continued operation during power outages or grid failures:

Guideline 6: Climate Change Adaptation and Resilience: Water infrastructure should be re-designed and upgraded to withstand the effects of climate change related events, such as droughts, flooding, sea-level rise, and extreme weather events. A diversity in water sources, such as rainwater harvesting, desalination, and wastewater reuse, can reduce dependency on vulnerable water sources and NaTech disasters. Moreover, risk management plans in case of flood (such as levees and buffer zones), and droughts (such as water rationing and storage), can ensure the operational ability of water management authorities.

Guideline 7: Secure Sustainable Funding for Infrastructure and Resilience: Authorities at the governmental level must secure increased public funding to modernize and protect water infrastructure, especially in high-risk areas. Private sector financing through public-private partnerships (PPPs) or green bonds to fund large-scale infrastructure projects and technological innovations could be considered. EU funding mechanisms (e.g., Horizon Europe, European Green Deal) must be actively exploited to support resilience-building projects and innovative water management solutions.

Guideline 8: Leverage Technological Innovation for Resilience: Water management authorities must invest in Machine learning and AI technologies to improve their efficiency. Processing the data from real-time water quantity and quality monitoring sensors can provide predictive analytics to identify infrastructure weaknesses and predict potential failures before they occur, enabling rapid response and risk mitigation. Automated water distribution systems that can quickly adapt to changes in supply, demand, or emergency conditions can also significantly improve resilience in the domain.

Guideline 9: Perform Extensive Testing Activities: Perform scenario-based testing to simulate real-world challenges like cyberattacks or extreme weather events. Scenario-based testing would enhance preparedness and reveal gaps in the current system. Moreover, as threats and technology evolve, regular reassessment of maturity levels will ensure that water infrastructure resilience strategies stay relevant and effective. Periodic re-evaluation helps identify emerging risks.

3.2. Regulatory Support Guidelines

Guideline 10: Improve Governance and Regulatory Compliance: Alignment with EU Directives: More steps are required towards ensuring compliance with the complex EU regulation framework, such as the Drinking Water Directive, the Water Framework Directive, and the Critical Entities Resilience (CER) Directive at the EU level. Regulation and Supervision technologies must be utilized to assure compliance in the era of digital transformation. In this framework, clear guidelines for incident reporting, compliance audits, and public transparency regarding water quality and infrastructure resilience is recommended. Establishing clear governance structures that disambiguate the roles and responsibilities between national, regional, and local authorities will help to avoid fragmentation in decision-making and improve crisis response.

3.3. Training, Reskilling and Upskilling Guidelines

Guideline 11: Conduct Regular Training and Drills: Water management authorities should launch ongoing training for water utility staff on emergency response, cybersecurity, risk assessment, and water treatment processes. In this framework, regular upskilling initiatives, simulations and drills (e.g., cyberattack scenarios, contamination events, natural disaster response) to test response plans and coordination efforts among agencies and operators is of paramount importance. Due to the strong interdependency with other CIs, the collaboration with other critical sectors (e.g., energy, healthcare) to conduct multi-agency drills to prepare for complex cross-sector emergencies is recommended.

Guideline 12: Increase Public Awareness and Engagement: The public is an essential stakeholder in the protection of CIs. Raising public awareness of the importance of water conservation, water safety, and infrastructure protection can improve the resilience of the infrastructure. In this direction, communities must be educated on how to report leaks, contamination, or security breaches. For this purpose, a communication strategy to keep the public informed during water supply interruptions or contamination events is recommended, including timely and accurate information on safety measures and restoration efforts. Finally, the engagement of local communities and stakeholders in water management decisions, particularly in vulnerable or underserved regions could increase awareness and participation.

3.4. Collaboration Guideline

Guideline 13: Strengthen Interagency and Cross-Sector Collaboration - Interagency Cooperation: Given the interdependencies with other sectors, cooperation between water utilities, public health agencies, emergency services, environmental regulators, and cybersecurity agencies to share resources, knowledge, and best practices is required. Effective collaboration with other critical sectors (e.g., energy, telecommunications, transportation) to address interdependencies and develop coordinated resilience strategies would strengthen the systemic resilience. The collaboration with private sector stakeholders can facilitate share of expertise, resources, and technology, particularly for cybersecurity and infrastructure upgrades.

Guideline 14: International Collaboration: Drinking water sector stakeholders must intensify their collaboration in order to cope with the rising scale of threats and the increasingly interconnected nature of the infrastructures of the sector. The collaboration shall target the development and piloting of risk resilience solutions, as well as the specification of common standards and agreed regulations.

4. EU-CIP Recommendations for R&I Activities and Roadmaps

The implementation of solutions in-line with the above-listed guidelines is essential for strengthening the resilience of financial infrastructure in ways that address the emerging technological, geopolitical, security and regulatory challenges. R&I activities play a significant role in the design, implementation, and validation of relevant solutions, as they provide opportunities for testing, experimentation, and validation. EU-CIP recommends the following measures that could foster the implementation of the above-listed guidelines.

Recommendation 1 – Specification and grading of CIP/CIR Maturity Levels: Organizations in the drinking water sector should assess their CIP maturity considering the sophistication, the automation and completeness of their technological solutions and related CIP policies. A classification into five maturity levels (“Excellent”, “Very Good”, “Good”, “Fair”, “Poor”) can be employed. The “Excellent” level indicates advanced CIP maturity addressing the earlier

outlined challenges (C1-C9) and implementing most of the given guidelines (G1-G13). On the other hand, “Poor” maturity indicates that most of the challenges and the solution guidelines remain unaddressed. Overall, an organization’s level of CIP maturity will determine the type and the density of R&I activities that the organization will have to employ.

Recommendation 2 – Matching Maturity Levels to R&I Roadmap: Water management organizations shall specify their R&I activities roadmap in-line with their maturity levels. The roadmap shall include activities addressed the above-listed guidelines (G1-G13). Organizations with poor CIP maturity and R&D density shall focus on the implementation on most of the outlined activities. Likewise, organizations with “Excellent” maturity shall emphasize the improvement and advance of existing measures.

Recommendation 3 – Clustering of Activities and Implementation Guidelines: The roadmaps must include research, technological development, regulatory auditing, and validation, as well as training and reskilling activities. In this direction, the roadmap shall include activities and support for all the different types of guidelines that were presented earlier. In terms of technological guidelines, solutions for Identity and Access Management (IAM), risk-based access control, multi-factor authentication, Security Information and Event Management (SIEM), Consent Management, Zero Trust Architecture and many more can be employed to support cyber-security functionalities like detection and response, cloud security, risk assessment and mitigation. In terms of regulatory support, measures for developing and validating CER compliance must be employed. In terms of training and upskilling, programs for both water management organizations and their customers must be designed and implemented.

Recommendation 4 – Foster Collaboration Activities at National and EU Scale: In-line with guideline G12, the R&I roadmaps of water management organizations must make provisions for collaborative activities at national and EU scale. This is key to reduce fragmentations and increase the capacity of the various institutions. Collaboration-related activities must strive to reduce costs by streamlining activities (including sharing of information), while at the same time consolidating best practices and lessons learnt. By sharing and coordination of resources more efficiency in the drinking water management chain can be achieved.

Recommendation 5 – Develop a Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework: Water Management organizations (including regulators) shall develop a framework for monitoring and assessing the impact of their roadmap, including for example metrics for assessing improvements in preparedness, timeliness, minimization of risks, cost reduction, effectiveness in regulatory compliance, reduction on business interruptions, increasing in consumer awareness, increase in consumer trust, speed for adaptation to the changing threat and regulatory landscape, as well as metrics for assessing the impact of the R&I roadmaps.

Figure 1: R&I RoadMap Development and Implementation Activities for Financial Organization with a 2030 Outlook

The role of the EU-CIP project

EU-CIP includes coordination and support activities that boost the implementation of the above-listed guidelines and roadmaps. Specifically:

- EU-CIP analyses the state of the art and the state of market to allow the identification of capability gaps and solutions that can help filling in these gaps. The present whitepaper falls in the scope of this analysis. Nevertheless, the project is also identifying and documented sector agnostic capability gaps that can be part of financial institutions R&I roadmaps.
- EU-CIP has documented relevant EU funded projects in CIP, along with other related research and scientific activities. This information is valuable backgrounds for the design of R&I roadmaps for financial organizations.
- EU-CIP has developed a range of innovation support services that can boost the development, deployment, operation, and commercialization of innovative CIP solutions for the financial sector. These services foster the transfer of technological solutions that adhere to the presented guidelines from the realm of research validation to scalable enterprise deployment.
- EU-CIP is developing and providing a range of training and upskilling services (e.g., a training catalogue, a series of CIP-related courses, a map of CIP-related skills profiles to learning paths) that can help financial sector professionals and consumers to improve their CIP skills.
- EU-CIP is supporting the development and build-up of the European CIP ecosystem, which provides opportunities for partnerships and collaborations across different organizations of the financial value chain.

Overall, EU-CIP fosters the development of CIP capabilities that will enable financial organizations to develop the technological capabilities, human capital, organizational processes, and collaborations required to address emerging CIP challenges with a 2030 outlook.

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